

Studies in Acid Anhydrides. Action of Semicarbazides on Anhydrides of Dibasic Acids.

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The action of *o*-diamines, benzidine, etc., upon anhydrides of dibasic acids has been studied by several authors (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 19, 330; Kollar, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 2880; Sircar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 397). The action of semicarbazide upon *o*-diketones, ketonic esters, etc., has also been studied (De, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 33; De and Dutta, *ibid.*, 1928, 5, 459; Bose, *ibid.*, 1924, 1, 51; 1925, 2, 95).

The action of semicarbazide on anhydrides of dibasic acids has been studied in this paper. Dunlap (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 27, 1091) obtained phthalyl semicarbazide (m. p. 262°) by heating a mixture of equimolecular proportion of semicarbazide hydrochloride and phthalic anhydride at 160°. The same compound has been prepared by the author by a different method. The presence of the free amino group in phthalyl semicarbazide has been proved by condensing it with benzaldehyde, another molecule of phthalic anhydride and preparing an acetyl derivative.

In the case of camphoric and diphenic anhydrides, dicamphoryl and di-diphenic semicarbazides are obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phthalyl semicarbazide was prepared by refluxing an alcoholic solution of phthalic anhydride with an equimolecular quantity of semicarbazide hydrochloride dissolved in water for 1½ hours on the water-bath. The almost colourless crystals separated and when recrystallised from acetic acid melted at 260-61° (Dunlap, *loc. cit.*, gives the m. p. 262°).

Benzylidenephthalyl semicarbazide.—Phthalyl semicarbazide (0.5 g.) was heated with benzaldehyde (0.5 c.c.) in an oil-bath with an air condenser for 15 minutes until a clear liquid was obtained. On cooling the mixture solidified and it was washed with alcohol and crystallised from alcohol as pale yellow needles, m. p. 170-71°. (Found: N, 13.73. $C_{16}H_{11}O_3N_3$ requires N, 14.33 per cent).

Triacetylphthalyl semicarbazide.—Phthalyl semicarbazide (0.5 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) for about an hour until it dissolved. Crystallised from dilute alcohol, it melts at 120-21°. (Found: N, 12.37. $C_{15}H_{14}O_5N_3$ requires N, 12.65 per cent).

Diphthalyl semicarbazide.—An intimate mixture of phthalyl semicarbazide and phthalic anhydride in equimolecular proportions and a little sodium acetate was heated on a sand-bath for 10 minutes. The fused mass was washed with hot water and the pale yellow solid was then extracted with alcohol several times. The residue was finally crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 300° after softening at 295°. (Found: N, 11.7. $C_{17}H_{19}O_5N_3$ requires N, 12.53 per cent).

Dicamphoryl semicarbazide.—An intimate mixture of camphoric anhydride (2 mols.) and semicarbazide hydrochloride (1 mol.) and a little sodium acetate was heated on a sand-bath for an hour and the melt washed twice with hot water. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. above 300°. (Found: N, 9.7. $C_{21}H_{29}O_5N_3$ requires N, 10.42 per cent).

Di-diphenic semicarbazide.—A mixture of diphenic anhydride (0.5 g.) with semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.25 g.) and a little sodium acetate was heated on a sand-bath to fusion for 10 to 15 minutes. The sticky mass was then washed with water and the residue crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 186-87°. (Found: N, 9.12. $C_{29}H_{17}O_5N_3$ requires N, 8.62 per cent).

Further work in this line is being continued.

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